

PEDAGOGICAL PRINCIPLES OF EDUCATION OF MUSICAL TASTE IN STUDENTS OF GRADE 5 - GENERAL SECONDARY SCHOOLS

Raimov Jur'atbek Ikrom o'g'li

State Conservatory of Uzbekistan

Teacher of the "Music Pedagogy" department

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Annotation: In this article, there are thoughts and opinions about the pedagogical foundations and features of training the musical taste of high school students in the "Music Culture" classes. Also, the scientific-theoretical aspects of the formation of musical feelings in students-young people are highlighted.

Key words: Music culture, aesthetics, musical activity, listening, pedagogical theory, music literacy.

Music is an important factor that develops the personality of students in general secondary schools, the personality of a person in general. serves to develop artistic taste, expand the scope of thought, develop musical feeling, and educate independence and initiative. The subject of musical culture is related to all subjects taught in general secondary schools, including literature, visual arts, physical education, labor and other subjects. The introduction of the State Education Standard in musical education, as well as in all educational subjects, allows full use of national musical heritage. These are reflected in popular folk tunes and songs, creative activities of singers and musicians, status, shashmaqom, epics and today's modern musical activity. Such opportunities of musical art serve as a unique and unrepeatable resource for educating the new generation and their development. From time immemorial, Eastern, including Uzbek music education, pedagogy and its excellent methods have been perfected on the example of teacher-disciple traditions.¹

The new educational content of music education based on the state education standards, together with the musical knowledge and skills of students, promotes the development of such qualities as observation, memory strengthening, visual imagination, creativity, independence, initiative, artistic and musical taste. provides Therefore, the new content of musical culture education envisages raising the young generation to the level of a cultured person who can inherit our musical heritage and perceive the wealth of universal music.

The main goal is for students to learn the art of music with all its elegance, mass music activities, perceive the artistic taste of music, sing, dance and create skills individually and in a group. Also, the main task of music education is to develop the musical talent of students, to increase their love and passion for music, to create the necessary conditions for the development of the talent of students interested in music, and to satisfy their artistic needs. . At the same time, in-depth study of the universal musical values of the peoples of the world ensures that the young generation can enjoy the cultural masterpieces of international prestige.

¹ Akbarov A.I. Dictionary of music. T.; Literary and art publishing house named after G. Ghulam. 1997.

The minimum requirements for the content of the educational subject of music culture consist of a set of theoretical and practical activities, and they determine the following topics: Elementary music literacy, activities of creators of musical works, music performers, music performance, activities of singing, choir, ensemble, orchestra and symphony orchestras, musical stage works, folk and professional music, composers and composers' work, Uzbek folk instruments to know the instruments, the creative activity of famous Uzbek folk musicians and singers, musical terms and expressions, music genres, master classical music, the music of the peoples of the East and the world, their famous representatives, status and shashmaqom, the activities of its famous performers, local Uzbek music and its famous performers, modernity in Uzbek national music and modern music, national pop music and its performers, refers to the mastery of our national music culture.

These topics are covered in the course of the lesson in the following educational activities through theoretical and practical exercises:

1. *Listening to music.*
2. *Sing as a group.*
3. *Music literacy.*
4. *Music creativity.²*

Listening and singing music is the basis of educational content. In addition to learning them through singing and listening activities, an opportunity is created for comprehensive learning and assimilation and expression of musical descriptions through musical activities, musical activities, and creative activities. Uzbek folk music samples of musical works of Uzbek composers and composers, composers of neighboring and world nations, shashmaqom branches, samples of local music styles will be heard. The activity of singing in a group is necessary for the development of students' musical learning ability and performance skills. In the process of group singing in the class, the student tries to control his voice performance, hear and observe the performance of the teachers, and cooperate with them.

Uzbek folk songs, songs by Uzbek composers and composers, folklore songs related to local music styles, songs by composers of world and sister nations, folklore songs related to local music styles, examples of status expressions they sing Listening to music, being able to distinguish a soloist from an accompaniment, being able to distinguish between an ensemble and an orchestra performance, being able to distinguish words and the timbre of words, developing musical taste and perception. It includes listening to samples of the works of Uzbek, sister and world composers.

² Abralo and M, Shamsiyeva Z., Musical culture. Recommendations and calendar subject plans for the introduction of an integrated curriculum. (Grades 1-7) T., - 2010 year.

Requirements for the level of preparation of 5th grade students:

Knowledge of local styles in national music practice and their connection with local dialects, other cultural and domestic traditions, specific performance styles and musical instruments in each local style, Fergana - Tashkent, Samarkand - Bukhara, Surkhandarya - Knowing the features of Kashkadarya and Khorezm styles, popular music genres (epic, big song, yallachilik), their famous performers, singers, understanding of status, studying shashmaqom, instruments and ways of saying. To know that ustozona music on the border of Uzbekistan has multi-disciplinary and local traditions, their similarities and compatibility, and the manifestation of local musical traditions in the field of modern music, composition and composer's creativity.

All these requirements to the content of education are important in developing students' knowledge, creative abilities, and developing their musical feelings. Because all activities of music education are related to general music performance.

The musical instrument played by the student, the melody of the song studied during the lesson, all these develop the feelings of the students and create a process of logical thinking in them. Analyzing the work musically, artistically and ideologically through conversation, and being able to describe the content of the work through listening will further increase the interest of the students. The role of class activities in the development and improvement of students' musical feeling in music culture classes of general secondary schools is important.

The requirements and tasks for these types of activities are fully specified in the content of the new program. The main activities of the new program are determined by the following, first of all, the specific topics of the lessons are derived from the main topics set for each quarter and help to understand the specific essence of music during the lesson, singing and music literacy exercises are not an independent part of the lesson, but it is accepted as a musical activity that reveals the topic of the lesson. Thirdly, in order to make the subject of the lesson interesting and to increase the effectiveness of education, dance and musical rhythmic movements, clapping and children's musical instruments - clapping, dancing, singing, etc. music activities are used. Due to the presence of game features at the core of these activities, they arouse great interest in students. All musical activities used in the lessons are an integral part of the lesson and a logical part. In this regard, the subject "Music" belongs to the type of complex (integral - mixed) lesson, and in it, musical activities that are subordinate to the general theme of the lesson and logically connected with each other are followed.

All types of musical activities are equally useful in developing and improving students' musical taste. The following music activities are followed during music lessons.³ **These are:** Music perception (listening), singing, music literacy, dance and rhythmic movements, clapping and playing instruments, and music creativity. Music perception plays an important role as a leading activity in class activities. It takes place in two cases. In the first case, a certain work is listened to and perceived, and its artistic descriptions are analyzed in a simple musical-pedagogical way related to the subject of the lesson. Through listening, one acquires knowledge of the musical features of the work (genre, structure, means of expression, performance) and artistic knowledge. In the second case, musical works are first listened to (perceived), then this or that activity is studied by singing more, and its artistic content

³ Akbarov A.I. Dictionary of music. T.; Literary and art publishing house named after G. Ghulam. 1997.

features are expressed in practical activities. For example, the song to be studied is first listened to by the teacher (also on tape) a couple of times, the character of the piece is discussed, then the study is started, dance music is listened to first, after the description of the melody is understood the expression of dance movements is studied. Often, the work is studied in combination of several activities (listening, singing, dance movements, etc.). This method of training provides an opportunity for a thorough study of the work and at the same time for the development of complex skills, and develops the musical feeling of the students during the training. In a music lesson, all activities are logically interconnected on the basis of a certain topic, as a result, a logical unity of the lesson is created. Music literacy is important as a theoretical unifying activity of all activities.

It is necessary to pay special attention to the fact that in the development and improvement of students' musical feeling, the role of music perception (listening) and music literacy activities is special. These two activities lead to the implementation of all the remaining activities with an integral connection to each other. Singing activity is necessary for the development of students' music-learning ability and performance skills. In the process of group singing in the class, the student controls his voice performance, listens and observes the performances of his friends and tries to sing along with them.

The activity of music creation is included in the program for the first time. This activity is of great importance for the development of musical thinking, research and creativity in children. This activity is carried out with such creative practices as tapping the circle around the teacher's performance, "conducting" the class performance, finding suitable movements (especially dance), "composing" a melody to a piece of poetry. This activity is important to increase attention to gifted students in the classroom, especially to satisfy their artistic needs. It is recommended to widely use game methods in the implementation of musical activities and creative activities. After all, these activities are more related to game features.

To sum up, musical activities are logically combined, form a whole in terms of content, and are important in developing students' musical feelings and musical taste.

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